

AN INVARIANT-BASED ANISOTROPIC THERMO-PLASTIC MATERIAL MODEL FOR SHORT FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the development of a new coupled thermomechanical invariant-based transversely-isotropic elastic-plastic constitutive model for short fibre reinforced composites. The invariant-based character of the developed model under multiaxial loading conditions allows the incorporation of the direction-dependent response of short fibre composites that result from the employed injection molding process. The nonlinear behavior of such composites is regarded using an anisotropic yield surface and non-associative plastic potential functions. From the computational standpoint, this novel coupled thermo-mechanical formulation is incorporated into the FE code FEAP through the user subroutine UEL, i.e. the constitutive model is integrated within a user-defined element. Finally, the model is examined by means of a simple benchmark test that shows the potential capabilities of the present formulation. This application is focused on the short fiber reinforced thermoplastic PA6GF30 that is typically used in a wide set of engineering applications, especially in car bodies and aeronautical constructions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent demands in achieving highly optimized structural components are gaining a significant relevance in different engineering applications, especially in the automotive and the aeronautical industries. One of the most innovative aspects regards the gradual incorporation of composite materials, which are able to achieve the realization of optimized and effective structural concepts in comparison to traditionally employed metals due to their excellent specific strength and stiffness ratios.

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastics can meet these requirements along with enabling an adequate adaptability to conform a wide range of design parts and withstand different external loading actions. In order to fully exploit the mechanical capabilities in terms strength and stiffness and the applicability of such composites, a thorough understanding of their structural performance is required. This issue is especially motivated as a consequence of the fact that the mechanical properties strongly depend upon the internal microstructural arrangement, i.e. fibre alignments at different locations within the component due to the fibre injection procedure employed. This anisotropic character influences the mechanical response of the specimen at service conditions, so that the accurate capturing of this characteristic response is of pivotal importance.

Many manufacturing processes involving short fiber reinforced thermoplastics and their posterior engineering applications are carried out at different temperatures. This for instance is the case of the tempered clinching joining technique that combines metallic and composite materials in order to produce hybrid structural components. The use of this technique to produce different parts motivates the development of fully-coupled material models that take into account the anisotropic character of

the composite component (generally glass fiber reinforced poly-amide PA6GF-x, where x stands for the fiber content of the specimen) and also incorporates the thermal effects.

In the related literature, there exists a significant number of works devoted to the theoretical formulation and numerical treatment of anisotropic plastic models. However, the thermo-mechanical coupling has received a limited attention up to now. In this context, most of the numerical investigations with regard to the thermo-mechanical analysis of composites with thermosetting resins have been devoted to the analysis of endless Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) using standard finite element formulations, see [1-2] and the references given therein.

Referred to polyamide-short fibre reinforced materials with thermoplastic resins, several works have investigated the influence of temperature, thickness and fibre orientation, the response under cycling loadings, among other aspects. In addition, further experimental studies analysed the fibre content and other features and their mechanical and thermo-mechanical response under static and cyclic loading conditions [3-5]. From a numerical perspective, most of these works only performed micromechanical investigations [6-7].

Based on the precedent arguments in this contribution, a novel invariant-based transversely isotropic thermo-plastic material model that displays the temperature dependent response of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics is presented. This model is an extension of the model presented in [8]. This extension addresses the full thermo-mechanical coupling in a thermodynamically consistent fashion, and also accounts for the effect of the plastic effects along the fiber direction using an enriched invariant set.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 deals with the thermodynamically consistent development of the thermo-mechanically coupled model. The FE formulation along with the description of the computational process is outlined in Section 3. A numerical example examines the material response under different temperature in combination with mechanical loadings is presented in Section 4. Finally, the main conclusions of this work and recommendations for future developments are given in Section 5.

2 COUPLED THERMOMECHANICAL TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC ELASTIC-PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR SHORT FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

The anisotropic behaviour of short fibre reinforced composites is motivated by the orientations of the fibres once they are embedded into the polymeric matrix, which is strongly influenced by the mould flow production process, see Fig. 1. The mathematical description of this anisotropic response has been traditionally carried out by means of a tensor-based representation in which the three dimensional fibre orientations is defined at each point in space using the second order tensor \mathbf{A} [8]. This structural tensor is generally obtained by applying the fiber distribution tensor to a group of n fibers in a limited range, and it can be defined as the dyadic product of the vectors of the preferred directions \mathbf{a} as follows

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{a} \rightarrow A_{ij} = a_i a_j. \quad (1)$$

The material response is therefore invariant with respect to arbitrary rotations around the direction \mathbf{a} , to reflections at planes parallel to the fibers and to reflections at those planes whose normal coincide with \mathbf{a} . These operations define the group of symmetries for transversely isotropic behavior.

2.1 Coupled thermomechanical transversely isotropic free energy definition

The coupled thermomechanical material model herein proposed relies on the basic assumption of infinitesimal elastic-plastic models, where an additive decomposition of the infinitesimal strain tensor ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$) into the elastic ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$) and the plastic parts ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$) is assumed

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p. \quad (2)$$

The linearized strain tensor is defined as the symmetric part of the displacement gradient $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} := \nabla^s \mathbf{u}$. The former decomposition scheme is also adopted for the entropy (η) of the system yielding

$$\eta = \eta^e + \eta^p, \quad (3)$$

where η^e and η^p identify the elastic and the plastic counterparts of the entropy. Motivated by the previous definitions, the free-energy function (ψ) is assumed to take the form

Figure 1: Micro-Computed Tomography of PA6-GF30 Plate.

$$\psi = \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \theta) = \psi^m(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) + \psi^{th}(\theta) + \psi^{thm}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \theta), \quad (4)$$

where ψ^m , ψ^{th} and ψ^{thm} stand for the mechanical, thermal and coupled thermomechanical terms of the total free-energy; $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ identifies the set of internal variables that account for hardening and θ denotes the temperature of the system. Particularizing Eq. (4) for transversely isotropic material response, the free-energy function reads

$$\psi = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e : \mathbb{C}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e - \mathbf{Z} : \mathbb{C}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e (\theta - \theta_0) + c_p \left[(\theta - \theta_0) + \theta \ln \left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0} \right) \right] + \psi^{hard}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}). \quad (5)$$

The last term of Eq. (5) is the hardening contribution to the free-energy, whereas \mathbf{Z} denotes the second order transversely isotropic thermal expansion tensor; c_p represents the heat capacity, θ_0 stands for the reference temperature and \mathbb{C}^e is the transversely isotropic elasticity tensor that can be obtained by taking the second derivative of the free energy function with respect to the strain tensor as follows

$$\mathbb{C}^e = \partial_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e}^2 \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{A}) = \lambda \mathbf{1} \otimes \mathbf{1} + 2\mu_T \mathbb{I} + \alpha(\mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} \otimes \mathbf{A}) + 2(\mu_L - \mu_T) \mathbb{I}_A + \beta \mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{A}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ and \mathbb{I} identify the second and the fourth order identity tensors, respectively, and $\mathbb{I}_A = A_{im} \mathbb{I}_{jmkl} + A_{jm} \mathbb{I}_{mikl}$, whereas $\lambda, \alpha, \beta, \mu_T, \mu_L$ are the five independent elastic constants.

2.2 The Clausius-Duhem inequality

The second law of thermodynamics in the form of the Clausius-Plank inequality is used to derive the constitutive equations of the model proposed herein. This condition states non-negative production of the internal dissipation (\mathcal{D}_{int}), which under non-isothermal conditions reads

$$\mathcal{D}_{int} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \dot{e} - \theta \dot{\eta} \geq 0, \quad (7)$$

where e is the internal energy that can be computed through the Legendre transformation as

$$e = \psi - \eta^e \theta. \quad (8)$$

According to standard arguments based on the Truesdell and Noll procedure [9] that must hold for all admissible processes, the use of Eqs. (3), (5), (7) and (8) leads to the following constitutive equations

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e} = \mathbb{C}^e : [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e - \mathbf{Z}(\theta - \theta_0)], \quad (9)$$

$$\eta^e = -\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\theta} = c_p \ln\left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0}\right) + \mathbf{Z} : \mathbb{C}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, \quad (10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Gamma} = \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \frac{\partial\psi^{hard}}{\partial\boldsymbol{\alpha}}. \quad (11)$$

Setting the stress-like vector hardening force $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$, the evaluation of the reduced dissipation inequality renders

$$\mathcal{D}_{int} = \mathcal{D}_m + \mathcal{D}_{th} = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} * \dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p + \theta \dot{\eta}^p \geq 0, \quad (12)$$

identifying $\mathcal{D}_m = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} * \dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p$ as the mechanical dissipation term and $\mathcal{D}_{th} = \theta \dot{\eta}^p$ as the thermal dissipation.

Phenomenologically, the heat flux equation is given by Fourier's law as follows

$$\mathbf{q} = -\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla[\theta], \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{K} denotes the second order transversely isotropic heat conductivity tensor.

2.3 Yield function

The thermoelastic domain \mathbb{E} can be defined assuming the maximum dissipation principle [10] as

$$\mathbb{E} = \{(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \theta) \mid f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) \leq 0\}. \quad (14)$$

The construction of the temperature dependent quadratic transversely isotropic yield function (f) accounting for the plastic deformation along the fiber direction can be expressed as

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) = \zeta_1 I_1 + \zeta_2 I_2 + \zeta_3 I_3 + \zeta_4 I_3^2 + \zeta_5 I_4 + \zeta_6 I_4^2 - 1 \leq 0, \quad (15)$$

where I_i ($i = 1,4$) are yield function stress invariants, each invariant represents an specific stress state. The invariants in Eq. (15) can be expressed in terms of the aforementioned decomposition of the stress tensor as follows [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{pind})^2 - \text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{pind})^2), \\ I_2 &= \text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{pind})^2), \\ I_3 &= \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - \text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}), \\ I_4 &= \frac{3}{2} \text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev}), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{pind}$ is the stress induces plasticity.

The temperature dependent parameters ζ_j ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \theta$) ($j = 1,6$) are given by

$$\zeta_j = \bar{\zeta}_j(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \theta_0)(1 - w_\zeta(\theta - \theta_0)), \quad (17)$$

with $\bar{\zeta}_j(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \theta_0)$ identifying the material parameters at the reference temperature, whereas w_ζ representing a set of weight functions. The determination of the six yield surface material parameters requires six different material tests. A compact representation of the yield function defined in Eq. (15) reads

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{eq}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbb{K} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{L} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} - 1 \leq 0, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbb{K} = \zeta_1 \mathbf{P}^{ind} + (\zeta_2 - \zeta_1) \mathbf{P}_A^{ind} + 2\zeta_4 (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) \otimes (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) + \frac{9}{2} \zeta_6 \mathbf{A}^{dev} \otimes \mathbf{A}^{dev}; \mathbf{L} = \zeta_3 (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) + \frac{3}{2} \zeta_5 \mathbf{A}^{dev} \quad (19)$$

The definition of the terms \mathbf{P}^{ind} , \mathbf{P}_A^{ind} and \mathbf{A}^{dev} are omitted here for the sake of the conciseness, see [8] for further details.

2.4 Plastic potential function

The present model additionally introduces the definition of a non-associative flow rule. Therefore, the evolution of the plastic strains is not governed by the gradient of the yield surface. This leads to the definition of the temperature dependent plastic potential function $g = g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta)$ that is usually denominated as plastic flow potential. Similar to the yield function definition but omitting the linear terms related to I_3 and I_4 , the plastic flow function can be defined as

$$g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) = \iota_1 I_1 + \iota_2 I_2 + \iota_3 I_3^2 + \iota_4 I_4^2 - 1 \leq 0, \quad (20)$$

where ι_k ($k = 1, 4$) are the set of temperature dependent plastic potential parameters. The determination of the plastic potential parameters relies on the required plastic behavior, e.g. plastic dilatancy and poisson's ratio. The compact version of the plastic flow function takes the form

$$g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbb{M} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} - 1 \leq 0, \quad (21)$$

with

$$\mathbb{M} = \iota_1 \mathbf{P}^{\text{ind}} + (\iota_2 - \iota_1) \mathbf{P}_A^{\text{ind}} + 2\iota_3 (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) \otimes (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) + \frac{9}{2} \iota_4 \mathbf{A}^{\text{dev}} \otimes \mathbf{A}^{\text{dev}}. \quad (22)$$

2.5 Internal variables evolution equations

Relying on the maximum energy plastic dissipation principle Eq. (12), the admissible stress tensor that maximize the plastic dissipation, the evolution equations of the internal variables are given by

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p = \gamma \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbb{M} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}; \quad \dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \gamma \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta)}{\partial \mathbf{r}}; \quad \dot{\eta}^p = \gamma \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta)}{\partial \theta} = \gamma \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}, \theta)}{\partial \mathbb{M}} \dots \sum_{k=1}^4 \frac{\partial \mathbb{M}}{\partial \iota_k} \frac{\partial \iota_k}{\partial \theta}, \quad (23)$$

where γ represents the consistency parameter (so called plastic multiplier) that satisfies the standard Kuhn-Tucker loading/unloading conditions

$$\gamma \geq 0; \quad f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\text{eq}}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) \leq 0; \quad \gamma f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\text{eq}}, \mathbf{A}, \theta) = 0. \quad (24)$$

Details concerning the integration algorithm of such equations following the backward Euler integration algorithm using the standard operator split [10] are omitted here for the sake of the brevity.

3 FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

In this section, the numerical aspects of the coupled thermomechanical transversely isotropic elastic-plastic material model outlined above. We construct a monolithic global solution procedure for the coupled problem that is governed by the balance of linear momentum and energy.

3.1 The global equations of coupled thermoplasticity

The first set of equations that govern the Initial Boundary Value Problem (IBVP) of coupled thermoplasticity is the balance of linear momentum. Thus, in the infinitesimal strain setting, these balance equations omitting the inertia effects read

$$\text{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}] + \mathbf{f}_v = \mathbf{0}, \quad (25)$$

where $\text{div}[\]$ denotes the divergence operator and \mathbf{f}_v the applied body forces. The second essential equation is the internal energy balance that can be expressed as

$$\dot{e} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \text{div}[\mathbf{q}] + r, \quad (26)$$

where r represents the prescribed heat source per unit of volume, respectively. Inserting Eqs. (7) and (8) into Eq. (26), the energy balance equation adopts the form

$$c_p \dot{\theta} + \theta \mathbf{Z} : \mathbb{C}^e : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e - r - \mathcal{D}_m + \text{div}[\mathbf{q}] = 0. \quad (27)$$

Standard boundary conditions are considered for Eqs. (25) and (27), see [10].

3.2 Finite element formulation

The finite element formulation of the coupled thermoplastic problem is accomplished by means of applying the standard Galerkin procedure to the strong form of the balance laws (see Eqs. (25) and (27) in Section 3.1) to obtain their respective weak forms. The strong forms of the balance of linear momentum and the balance of energy are weighted with the virtual displacements ($\delta \mathbf{u}$) and the virtual temperature ($\delta \theta$) functions, respectively, and then integrated over the body volume (Ω)

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \text{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}] \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{f}_v \, d\Omega = 0, \quad (28)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, c_p \dot{\theta} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, \theta \mathbf{Z} : \mathbb{C}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e \, d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, r \, d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, \mathcal{D}_m \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, \text{div}[\mathbf{q}] \, d\Omega = 0. \quad (29)$$

The term $\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \text{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]$ is opened as $\text{div}[\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}] - \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}$, and the term $\delta \theta \, \text{div}[\mathbf{q}]$ is further elaborated as $\text{div}[\delta \theta \mathbf{q}] - \nabla[\delta \theta] \cdot \mathbf{q}$, where $\nabla[\]$ stands for the spatial gradient operator. These expressions are substituted into (28) and (29), and after applying the Gauss and Cauchy Theorems and the prescribed boundary conditions, one can obtain

$$G_u = \int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \, d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, d\partial\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{f}_v \, d\Omega = 0, \quad (30)$$

$$G_{\theta} = \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, c_p \dot{\theta} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, \theta \mathbf{Z} : \mathbb{C}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e \, d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, r \, d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \theta \, \mathcal{D}_m \, d\Omega + \int_{\partial\Omega} \delta \theta \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, d\partial\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \nabla[\delta \theta] \cdot \mathbf{q} \, d\Omega = 0, \quad (31)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ is the prescribed traction vector and \mathbf{n} represents the outer normal vector. The temperature rate $\dot{\theta}$ within the integration interval $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$ is given by $\dot{\theta} = (\theta_{n+1} - \theta_n) / \Delta t$.

The arbitrary body (Ω) is discretized into n_e non-overlapping elements: $\Omega \approx \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \Omega_{e,i}$. The kinematic and the thermal fields are interpolated within the element domain from the nodal (\mathbf{d} representing the nodal displacements and $\hat{\theta}$ identifying the nodal temperature) values using the standard shape functions $N^A(\boldsymbol{\xi})$, where $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \{\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3\}$ denote the natural coordinates of the master node element. The interpolation schemes corresponding to the displacements and the temperature read

$$\mathbf{u} \approx \sum_{A=1}^{n_n} N^A(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \mathbf{d}_A; \quad \theta \approx \sum_{A=1}^{n_n} N^A(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \hat{\theta}_A \quad (32)$$

where n_n is the number of nodes of the elements of the discretization; \mathbf{d}_A and $\hat{\theta}_A$ denote the displacement and temperature of the node A . It is worth mentioning that the present interpolation scheme complies with the Bubnov-Galerkin method, in which the same interpolation functions are used for the real and virtual displacements and thermal fields. After the insertion of Eq. (32) into Eqs. (30) and (31), the linearization procedure of such system of equations can be accomplished through the directional derivative concept [10], that generally reads

$$\Delta G_u(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) = G_u(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) + \Delta G_{u,d}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) \Delta \mathbf{d} + \Delta G_{u,\theta}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) \Delta \hat{\theta} \quad (33)$$

$$\Delta G_{\theta}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) = G_{\theta}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) + \Delta G_{\theta,d}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) \Delta \mathbf{d} + \Delta G_{\theta,\theta}(\mathbf{d}, \delta \mathbf{d}, \hat{\theta}) \Delta \hat{\theta} \quad (34)$$

Note that $\Delta \mathbf{d}$ and $\Delta \hat{\theta}$ denote the incremental nodal displacements and temperatures, respectively. The fully coupled simultaneous solution takes the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{dd} & \mathbf{K}_{d\theta} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\theta d} & \mathbf{K}_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{d} \\ \Delta \hat{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_d \\ \mathbf{R}_{\theta} \end{bmatrix}; \quad (35)$$

where K_{dd} , $K_{d\theta}$, $K_{\theta d}$, $K_{\theta\theta}$ represent the element stiffness matrices; \mathbf{R}_d and \mathbf{R}_{θ} identify the element residual vectors. Three nonlinear quantities need to be linearized with respect to strain and temperature, leading to the definition of six different consistent tangent terms. The specific expressions of all these derivations are omitted here for the sake of brevity. The nonlinear set of equations given by Eq. (35) has been implemented into the FE code FEAP using the user-defined subroutine UEL. In particular, a 20-node element has been employed for this purpose in order to minimize prospective locking effects.

4 REPRESENTATIVE NUMERICAL APPLICATION

In the following a numerical example is given in order to illustrate the capabilities of the coupled transversely thermo-plastic model formulated above to reproduce the thermomechanical response of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The algorithmic model previously presented was numerically implemented into an extended version of the FE code FEAP. Since not all the required material tests are available, reasonable assumptions are made to obtain rational simulation results. This example aims to simulate the uniaxial tension test in fiber direction of PA6GF30 subjected to different thermal conditions.

The domain for the problem is a tensile specimen with overall length of 60 mm, width of 20 mm, distance between shoulders of 35.4 mm and 1 mm thickness. The implicit numerical application consisted of 615 elements subjected to mechanical and thermal loadings. The higher-order full integrated element topology (3D 20-node brick element) was used for the spatial discretization. The geometric and mesh are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Geometry and Mesh of PA6-GF30 Plate.

Fig. 3 shows the simulation results of uniaxial tension at different temperature ranges from room temperature ($\approx 20^\circ\text{C}$) to 80°C . The plotted Stresses vs. Strains are obtained from an element in the middle of the specimen (parallel range) to avoid the triaxiality within the vicinity of the clamps and to have a more or less uniaxial stress state. The simulation result at room temperature is compared with the experimental data obtained by IFUM for PA6GF30. The simulation shows very good agreement with the test data.

With regard to the numerical features, the model is quite stable and robust. No severe convergence difficulties to achieve equilibrium solutions were found along the computation.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This contribution presents the development of a new invariant-based transversely isotropic thermo-plastic material model that displays the temperature dependent response of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics is presented. The model preserves the thermodynamic consistency and has been successfully implemented into the FE code FEAP using the user-defined routine UEL. Finally, the capabilities of the present formulation have been examined using a simple benchmark example that shows the robustness for modelling the thermos-mechanical response of short fiber reinforced composites. Further investigations on this area would regard the application of the model to more complex structures and loading conditions.

Figure 3: Uniaxial Tension Test Simulation of PA6GF30 under Various Thermal Loadings

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